

BRIDGING AYURVEDA AND MODERN MEDICINE: A CASE STUDY ON THE ADD-ON EFFECT OF KANCHNAR SHUNTI VATI WITH THYROXINE IN HYPOTHYROIDISM¹*Patil Tanvi, ²Kurande Vrinda¹PG Scholar, Department of Kayachikitsa, PDEAS College of Ayurved Research Center and Hospital, Sector no25, Pradhikaran, Nigadi, Pune -411044, (Maharashtra) India.²Associate Professor, Department of Kayachikitsa, PDEAS College of Ayurved research center and Hospital, Sector no25, Pradhikaran, Nigadi, Pune-411044, (Maharashtra) India.***Corresponding Author: Patil Tanvi**

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20455464>**How to cite this Article:** ¹*Patil Tanvi, ²Kurande Vrinda. (2026). Bridging Ayurveda and Modern Medicine: A Case Study on The Add-On Effect of Kanchnar Shunti Vati with Thyroxine In Hypothyroidism. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 12(6), 191-193.

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Article Received on 15/04/2026

Article Revised on 05/05/2026

Article Published on 01/06/2026

ABSTRACT

Hypothyroidism is a common endocrine disorder characterized by insufficient thyroid hormone production, leading to metabolic slowing and multisystem involvement.^[4] While Levothyroxine (thyroxine) remains the standard treatment, many patients continue to experience residual symptoms. Ayurveda offers potential adjunct therapies targeting metabolic correction and glandular balance. This case study evaluates the add-on effect of Kanchnar Shunti Vati alongside thyroxine in a diagnosed case of hypothyroidism. The combined approach demonstrated improvement in clinical symptoms and biochemical parameters, suggesting a synergistic benefit. The line of treatment with specific target to Rasavaha, Mamsavaha, Medovaha, Manovaha Srotas as well as Vata-Kapha Nashaka, Agnideepan, Sroto Shodhana, Vatanuloman, Amapachan treatment should be administered in hypothyroidism. This highlights the scope of integrative medicine in Hypothyroidism.

KEYWORDS: Hypothyroidism, Ayurveda, Kanchnar Shunti Vati, Thyroxine, Agnimandya, Dhatwagni vikriti Integrative Medicine.**INTRODUCTION**

Hypothyroidism affects a significant portion of the population, especially women. Standard treatment involves lifelong hormone replacement therapy with Levothyroxine. However, persistent symptoms like fatigue, weight gain, and menstrual irregularities are frequently reported despite normalized thyroid function tests.^[4]

Jatharagni is the leader of all factors concerned With digestion and metabolism in the living body. Hypothyroidism is a progressive disorder of thyroid gland due to an insufficient amount of thyroid hormone. The thyroid is an important part of human endocrine system which is responsible for regulation of oxygen use, BMR, cellular metabolism and growth and development. The major function of thyroid gland is to act as spark for

the maintenance of oxidative metabolism in most tissues. In Ayurveda parlance, this is attributed as function of Agni. If we try to correlate the pathogenesis of hypothyroidism according to principles of Ayurveda we found that it is basically caused due to dysfunction of Agni.

In Ayurveda, hypothyroidism can be correlated with Agnimandya, Kapha-Vata imbalance, and Medo Dhatu Dushti. Herbal formulations such as Kanchnar Guggulu and its variants, including Kanchnar Shunti Vati, are traditionally used in Granthi and Galganda disorders.

This study explores the clinical effectiveness of combining Ayurvedic intervention with conventional therapy.

CASE PRESENTATION**Patient Information**

- Age: 24 years
- Gender: Female
- Chief complaints:
- Bharruddhi(Weight gain)(6 kg in 6 months)
- Hair fall
- Dry skin

Ashtavidh pariksha

Nadi -78/min BP-120/70mmhg
 Mala-samyak
 Mutra-samyak
 Jivha -niram
 Shabda -spashta
 Sparsha-Anushna
 Drik-prakrut
 Akrti-sthul
 Prakruti-pittapradhan

Nutritional status -mixed diet**Medical History**

- Diagnosed with hypothyroidism 1 years ago
- On Tab. Thyroxine 25 mcg daily

Baseline Investigations

- TSH: 8.4 mIU/L
- T3: 0.86ng/ml low normal
- T4: 9.13ug/dl

RESULTS

Parameter	Before	After
TSH	8.412 uIU/ml	5.32 uIU/ml
Weight	+6kg	-3kg
Hairfall	Moderate	Reduced
Dry skin	Present (sever dryness)	Improved (mild dryness,better texture)

DISCUSSION

The observed improvement may be attributed to the pharmacological properties of Kanchnar Shunti Vati:

- Kanchnar (Bauhinia variegata): Anti-inflammatory, glandular detoxifier
- Shunthi (Zingiber officinale): Enhances digestion (Deepana-Pachana)

From an Ayurvedic perspective, the formulation corrects Agnimandya and clears Srotorodha, which are key in hypothyroidism pathogenesis. These drugs are having Katu, Kashya Rasa which makes the drugs to act as Kaphashamaka, Pitta Vardhaka and Ama Dosha Hara drugs. These Rasas have tendency of reducing Kapha and Medas. Katu rasa removes the obstruction and thus correct the Srotorodha. Kashya rasa has Lekhna Guna that scraps out excessive Kapha and Meda from Srotasa. So, it is apparent that by virtue of their Rasas, these drugs are likely to act as Kaphashamaka and Medohara, thus have beneficial effects in management hyperlipidaemia, obesity etc which is associated with Hypothyroidism.^[193] Ushna Veerya of Shunthi increases basal metabolic weight, oxygen consumption and

INTERVENTION**Modern Treatment**

- Continued Tab. Thyroxine 25 mcg once daily (empty stomach)

Ayurvedic Add-on Therapy

- Kanchnar Shunti Vati – 1 tablets twice daily after meals
- Duration: 2months

Diet & Lifestyle Advice

- Avoid heavy, oily, and cold foods
- Include warm, light, easily digestible diet
- Regular physical activity (30 min/day)
- Stress management (Pranayama, Yoga)

Assessment Criteria

- Classical features of hypothyroidism
1. Weight monitoring
 2. Cold intolerance
 3. Hairfall
 4. Dry and coarse skin
 5. Puffiness
- Thyroid function tests (TSH, T3, T4)

OBSERVATIONS

- Significant reduction in TSH levels
- Improvement in metabolic symptoms
- No adverse effects reported

accelerate the breakdown of fat at mitochondrial level . Sunthi undergoes Madhur Vipaka and thus has anabolic effect on the body. Sunthi acts by direct enrichment of the nutritional quality of the Rasa Dhatu and in turn helps in improving tissue nourishment and in production of better qualities of Dhatus, due to its Madhura Vipaka and Snigdha Guna. In addition Kanchanra itself is given the synonym of 'Gandari that means it arrests the growth of the cyst.

The combination with thyroxine may provide

- Symptomatic relief beyond biochemical correction
- Improved metabolic activity
- Better patient quality of life

CONCLUSION

This case study suggests that Kanchnar Shunti Vati as an add-on to thyroxine therapy may enhance clinical outcomes in hypothyroidism. Integrative approaches combining Ayurveda and modern medicine could offer a more holistic and effective management strategy.

Limitations

- Single case study
- Short duration
- Larger randomized controlled trials needed

Future Scope

- Multi-center clinical trials
- Dose standardization
- Mechanism-based studies

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